

Impedance-based TRACT assay for SLC6A2 using HEK293 JumpIn SLC6A2 OE cells

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Assay description

The Impedance-based 'transporter activity through receptor activation (TRACT) assay detects transport activity of the norepinephrine transporter (NET, SLC6A2) via GPCR-mediated changes in cell morphology. The assay is based on the principal that Co-expressed GPCR-SLC pair share a common agonist/substrate. Activation of a GPCR will result in changes in cell morphology that are detected as changes in cellular impedance using the xCELLigence RTCA system. Active SLCs transport part of the substrate into the cell leaving a lower extracellular concentration of agonist to activate the GPCR and consequently an attenuated GPCR-mediated response can be observed which reflects SLC activity (Fig. 1). Treatment with NET inhibitors will enhance the GPCR response which is a measure of SLC inhibition. The TRACT assay can be used to determine the potency (EC₅₀) of (endogenous) G protein-coupled receptor (GPCR) agonists on JumpIn-NET cells and enables the determination of inhibitory potency (IC₅₀) of NET inhibitors.

Figure 1. Principal of a Impedance-based TRACT assay that relies on a shared substrate/agonist for the SLC-GPCR pair. 1) Activation of a GPCR by a agonist results in changes in cell morphology which can be detect using an xCELLigence real-time cell analyzer (RTCA) system as changes in cellular impedance. 2) Upon co-expression of a SLC, the shared substrate can be taken up by the SLC resulting in a reduced extracellular substrate/agonist concentration thereby attenuating the GPCR response. 3) Inhibition of the SLC by an inhibitor restores GPCR action to level without SLC present.

Assay protocol

Label-free TRACT assays were performed using the xCELLigence real-time cell analysis (RTCA) technology as reported previously²². Impedance values, which are measured continuously at a frequency of 10 kHz, for each well are converted by the RTCA software to the dimensionless parameter Cell Index (CI) using the following formula:

$$CI = \frac{(Z_i - Z_0)\Omega}{15\Omega}$$

where Z_i is the impedance at any given time point and Z_0 is the baseline impedance that is measured at the start of each experiment²⁷.

Assays were performed at 37°C and 5% CO₂ in 96-well E-plates in a final volume of 100 µl per

well. Background impedance was measured in 45 μ l (one compound addition) or 40 μ l (two compound additions) culture medium prior to cell seeding. Compounds were added in 5 μ l per addition using a VIAFLO 96 handheld electronic 96 channel pipette (INTEGRA Biosciences, Tokyo, Japan). All conditions were tested in duplicate on each plate.

Cell preparation and monitoring

JumpIn-NET cells were grown to 70-80% confluence on the day of the experiment. Baseline impedance was measured using culture medium with or without 1 μ g/ml doxycycline (dox). Cells were seeded in E-plates at 60,000 cells/well in culture medium. Cells were left to sink to the bottom for 30 minutes at room temperature before placing the E-plate in the recording station at 37°C. Cells were left to grow overnight for 22-24 hr while recording impedance every 15 minutes.

Cell pretreatment

In GPCR antagonist experiments, cells were pretreated by the addition of a single concentration (1 μ M) of yohimbine (alpha-2 adrenergic receptor antagonist), propranolol (non-selective beta adrenergic receptor antagonist) or a 1:1 mix of both antagonists in DMSO. In TRACT assays, cells were pretreated with either a single concentration (1 μ M) of nisoxetine (high affinity NET inhibitor²⁸) or six increasing concentrations of a NET inhibitor. Due to strict local regulations, cocaine could only be tested in the TRACT assay and not in the fluorescent substrate uptake assay. For all pretreatments DMSO was kept at 0.1% per well and impedance was measured for 1 h prior to substrate addition.

Cell stimulation

Cells with or without pretreatment were stimulated by the addition of either norepinephrine (NE), dopamine (DA) or epinephrine (EP) as a substrate dissolved in 1mM ascorbic acid in PBS. Note, ascorbic acid was used as an antioxidant for the monoamine neurotransmitter substrates²⁹. In antagonist experiments cells were stimulated with a submaximal concentration (EC₈₀) of substrate (i.e. 10 μ M NE; 100 μ M DA; 10 μ M EP). In TRACT assays cells were stimulated with seven increasing concentrations of substrate to determine substrate potency. To determine the inhibitory potencies of NET inhibitors, cells were stimulated with a submaximal (EC₂₀) concentration of substrate (i.e. 1 μ M NE; 3.16 μ M DA; 1 μ M EP). For a total of 30 min after stimulation, impedance was measured initially every 15 seconds for 25 minutes and then every minute.

TRACT assay HTS validation

The TRACT assay was assessed for reproducibility, robustness and amenability to high-throughput screening (HTS) according to methods described previously in assay guidance manuals³⁰. Three 96-well E-plates were run consecutively per day on three separate days. Cells were induced with 1 μ g/ml dox at the start of each experimental run. After cell seeding, E-plates were left at room temperature for 30 min and subsequently placed inside an incubator for 22 h. Each E-plate had an alternating interleaved layout consisting of high, mid and low signals for which cells were pretreated with either 1 μ M nisoxetine, 10 nM nisoxetine or vehicle (DMSO), respectively. After 1 h pretreatment, all wells were stimulated with a submaximal (EC₂₀) concentration (1 μ M) of NE. Impedance was recorded for 30 min after substrate addition. Immediately after recording the NE response the next E-plate was inserted in the RTCA recording station. Compound additions were done using a VIAFLO 96 handheld electronic 96 channel pipette. All other handlings were performed manually.

Data analysis: Experimental data was recorded using RTCA Software v2.0 or v2.1.1 (ACEA Biosciences). For analysis of substrate-induced responses CI values were normalized to the time point prior to substrate addition to obtain normalized CI (nCI) values. Data were exported from RTCA Software and all subsequent analyses were performed in GraphPad Prism v8.1.1 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA). The nCI values of vehicle-only controls were subtracted from all other data points to baseline-correct for any substrate-independent effects. Substrate-induced responses were quantified by taking the net area under the curve (AUC) of the first 30 min after substrate addition. The apparent potency values of NET substrates and the inhibitory potency values of NET inhibitors were obtained by fitting the AUC data with non-linear regression to a sigmoidal concentration-effect curve with a variable pseudo-Hill slope.

Additional information

Target data

SLC	SLC6A2
Synonyms	Norepinephrine transporter (NET)
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 6, (Monoamine transporter subfamily)
UniProt ID	Canonical form (P23975-1, isoform 1)
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE02FZ-0 (HEK-SLC6A2-WTOE-p1)

Assay data

	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	IC ₅₀ = 0.63 μM
	Compound name (6)	Desipramine hydrochloride
	PubChem CID	65327
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma #D3900
	Mode of action	Inhibitor
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	IC ₅₀ = 0.0063 μM
	Compound name (7)	GBR12909
	PubChem CID	3455
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Toronto research chemicals #G268005
	Mode of action	Inhibitor
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	IC ₅₀ = 0.79 μM
	Compound name (8)	Maprotiline hydrochloride
	PubChem CID	71478
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Santa cruz biotechnology #SC-200156
	Mode of action	Inhibitor
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	IC ₅₀ = 0.05 μM
	Compound name (9)	Milnacipran hydrochloride
	PubChem CID	163701
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Target mol #T1189
	Mode of action	Inhibitor
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	IC ₅₀ = 0.05 μM
	Compound name (10)	Nisoxetine hydrochloride
	PubChem CID	134453
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Santa cruz biotechnology #SC-203646
	Mode of action	Inhibitor
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	IC ₅₀ = 0.005 μM
	Compound name (11)	Nortriptyline hydrochloride
	PubChem CID	441358
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Target mol #T1327
	Mode of action	Inhibitor
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	IC ₅₀ = 0.04 μM
	Compound name (12)	Reboxetine mesylate
	PubChem CID	127150

	Vendor (catalogue #)	Toronto research chemicals #R142000
	Mode of action	Inhibitor
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	IC ₅₀ = 0.005 μM
<p>Figure 13: Dose-response curves for compound 13. The y-axis is % AUC cellular response (ranging from -20 to 120) and the x-axis is log [norepinephrine] (M) (ranging from 0 to -3). Two curves are shown: +dox (filled circles) and -dox (open circles). Both curves show a sigmoidal increase in response with increasing concentration, with the -dox curve shifted to the left of the +dox curve. Error bars represent standard deviation.</p>	Compound name (13)	L-(-)-Norepinephrine (+)-bitartrate salt monohydrate
	PubChem CID	3047796
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma #N5785
	Mode of action	substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	-dox EC ₅₀ = 0.4 μM +dox EC ₅₀ = 6.3 μM
<p>Figure 14: Dose-response curves for compound 14. The y-axis is % AUC cellular response (ranging from -20 to 120) and the x-axis is log [dopamine] (M) (ranging from 0 to -3). Two curves are shown: +dox (filled squares) and -dox (open squares). Both curves show a sigmoidal increase in response with increasing concentration, with the -dox curve shifted to the left of the +dox curve. Error bars represent standard deviation.</p>	Compound name (14)	Dopamine hydrochloride
	PubChem CID	65340
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma #8502
	Mode of action	substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	-dox EC ₅₀ = 7.9 μM +dox EC ₅₀ = 20 μM
<p>Figure 15: Dose-response curves for compound 15. The y-axis is % AUC cellular response (ranging from -20 to 120) and the x-axis is log [epinephrine] (M) (ranging from 0 to -3). Two curves are shown: +dox (filled triangles) and -dox (open triangles). Both curves show a sigmoidal increase in response with increasing concentration, with the -dox curve shifted to the left of the +dox curve. Error bars represent standard deviation.</p>	Compound name (15)	(-)-Epinephrine (+)-bitartrate salt
	PubChem CID	5815
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma E4375
	Mode of action	substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	-dox EC ₅₀ = 0.4 μM +dox EC ₅₀ = 4.0 μM

Discussion

The impedance-based TRACT assay displays a shift in EC_{50} upon doxycycline-induction of NET indicating that norepinephrine, dopamine and epinephrine are transported into the cell resulting in a lower extracellular concentration of Dopamine and consequently a reduced GPCR activation. As the best shift is observed for norepinephrine this is the preferred substrate for inhibitor studies.

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).
- <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-91700-7>